

D1.1 – User requirements & regulations for fertilizer production and use

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1. Introduction

ReLEAF project aims to formulate, produce, and demonstrate agronomic and environmental performance of safe, sustainable, and efficient BBFs (bio-based fertilizers) produced from widely available bio-wastes, which can compete in the European and global fertilizers market. To achieve this ambitious goal, the project needs to work and provide relevant data to overcome different barriers that might be a threat for its real implementation. It was identified two non-technical barriers that may affect ReLEAF BBFs marketability: the regulatory framework and the acceptance of the obtained products, as they are produced from non-conventional sources. This document presents the regulatory framework and end-user requirements for this type of fertilizer, and it constitutes the deliverable D1.1. produced within WP1.

In this regard, this deliverable looks at the current regulation to provide a complete picture of how the EU regulates fertilizing products with special attention to the legislation relevant for ReLEAF bio-based ingredients. Therefore, the deliverable includes: (1) analysis of main EU regulation, with special attention to Fertilizing Products Regulation (FPR) 2019/1009 including a description of raw material categories (CMC) and product categories (PFC); (2) analysis of other European regulations linked to EU 2019/1009 such as fertilizer labelling and CE conformity assessment, among others; (3) analysis of organic farming regulatory framework; (4) assessment of national regulations on the countries part of the consortium (France, Spain, Italy, Germany, Portugal, Poland, and Switzerland) and mutual recognition; and (5) discussion of regulatory aspects of each biobased ingredient and fertilizers produced as part of ReLEAF.

Moreover, this deliverable is completed by the analysis of end-user requirements that will guide the development of ReLEAF products and the project strategy towards stakeholder engagement and social acceptance.

This delivery establishes the framework and the basis for ReLEAF to work towards clear evidence-based information regarding the quality and performance of the ingredients and end-products obtained to ensure their market uptake.

2. Regulatory framework

Fertilizer producers can choose to market products at European or national scale, whereby either European or national regulations apply. At European level, CE-marked fertilizers, i.e. which conform to the European Regulation UE 2019/1009 and their complemented regulations (**shortened FPR: Fertilizing Products Regulation**), may circulate freely within the European market. The Fertilizing Products Regulations are regularly updated by a new act to introduce a new complement or to give more precision and grouped together in one consolidated document and published by the European Commission.

At national scale, producers can market fertilizers according to national regulations. However, they can use mutual recognition to market the product in another European country.

Requirements and procedures for CE marking are described in section 2.1 (European Regulation UE 2019/1009) and 2.2 (other relevant regulations). For using products in organic farming, additional regulations apply, which are outlined in section 2.3. A selection of national regulations is presented in section 2.4.

2.1. Overview of the FPR 2019/1009

The actual European Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 (FPR) is intended to provide a harmonised framework for the fertilizer market in Europe. This regulation came into force in July 2022 and replaces the previous Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003.

The aims of the new regulation are:

- to create a **single harmonized market** for fertilizers in Europe, by establishing common rules for all Member States.
- to define a **CE-marking**, which allows products to move freely across the European single market.
- to lay down **safety criteria** guaranteeing the absence of risks to human or animal health or the environment (also lowering authorized thresholds to improve environmental quality).
- to enhance **fertilizers' effectiveness**, i.e. fertilizers that provide the exact amount of nutrients needed by plants while minimizing losses, with a view to **precision farming**.
- to promote the **circular economy** and **resources sustainability** by extending its scope to fertilizers produced from **organic** renewable or recycled raw materials, which represents a major change compared to the previous regulation.

The European Regulation gives precise definitions of different **functional categories of products** (PFC) and their **component material categories** (CMC). It lays down safety and quality requirements for each type of fertilizer in terms of composition, innocuousness and efficacy. This regulation outlines also requirements for fertilizer labelling by including safe use and describing procedures for conformity assessments.

In addition, Article 19 of UE 2019/1009 specifies that *“this Regulation lays down criteria in accordance with which material that constitutes waste, as defined in Directive 2008/98/EC, can cease to be waste, if it is contained in a compliant EU fertilizing product. In such cases, the recovery operation under this Regulation shall be performed before the material ceases to be waste, and the material shall be considered to comply with the conditions laid down in Article 6 of that Directive and therefore to have ceased to be waste from the moment that the EU declaration of conformity was drawn up”*, thus establishing clear directives to be accomplished according to the End of Waste criteria.

2.1.1. Component Material Categories (CMC)

European Regulation 2019/1009 has introduced a classification system for the raw materials used in the manufacturing process of fertilizers, known as CMC. These CMCs make it easier to characterize fertilizers and ensure that they comply with regulatory requirements.

All component materials entering the composition of an EU fertilizer must belong to a CMC. Each CMC implies some specific requirements (REACH registration, “end-of-waste” criteria, animal by-products regulation). Currently (March 2025), the FPR regulation defines 15 CMC.

Description of these CMC is given below. Detailed characteristics are described in the consolidated document.

CMC 1: Virgin substances and mixtures of materials

This category corresponds to materials extracted or manufactured and which have not already been used or recycled. They can be of natural or synthetic origin. This category of materials excludes waste and by-products within the meaning of regulation 2008/98/EC. It also excludes substances which have ceased to be wastes and substances formed from precursors which have ceased to be wastes. Finally, this CMC also excludes all substances that correspond to any other CMCs of European Regulation 2019/1009. This category nevertheless includes certain polymers which result from a polymerisation process which has taken place in nature.

All substances, other than those which are exempted according to Annex IV or certain cases of Annex V, must be registered in Reach including substances marketed at less than one Ton/year. Registration in Reach must include a chemical safety report covering use as a fertilizer.

European Regulation 2019/1009 also presents specific requirements for certain substances in this category such as urease, nitrification and denitrification inhibitors or substances intended to enhance the long-term availability of nutrient elements.

CMC 2: Plants, plant parts or plant extracts

CMC 2 includes whole plants, parts of plants (stems, leaves, roots) or plant extracts used as fertilizers (note that in this regulation, algae and fungi are included in “plants”, but cyanobacteria (blue/green algae) are excluded). These tissues have only undergone ‘simple’ (empirical) treatment: mechanical (grinding, sieving, pressing, etc.), extraction (water, CO₂), thermal (cold or hot <100°C). Any additive other than water is prohibited as well as any ‘complex’ treatment (in this case, the material will belong

to CMC 6). Examples of materials for this CMC are crop residues, dead leaves, fruit pulp, rapeseed meal or seed cake.

CMC 3: Compost

Composts are defined as products obtained by the controlled biological decomposition of organic matter under aerobic conditions. Aerobic composting can include one or more inputs. Biowastes (within the meaning of Directive 2008/98/EC resulting from separate bio-waste collection at source), living or dead microorganisms (that have not been treated or treated by a 'simple' process), are authorised. Materials from municipal wastes, municipal or industrial sludges are prohibited. Some animal by-products and some composted or digested materials can be used. Additives can be used if they are compliant with Reach regulation (EC 1907/2006) without exceeding 5% of total composted material biomass.

In addition, composting conditions are also specified by the UE 2019/1009 regulation, especially temperature conditions to be respected.

Thresholds are given:

- Macroscopic impurities (glass, metal or plastic) are limited to 3 g/Kg DM
- The sum of glass, metal and plastics is limited to 5g/Kg DM
- HAPs are limited to 6 mg/Kg DM.

CMC 4: Fresh crop digestate

This category concerns anaerobic digestion of plants (including algae and excluding blue/green algae) grown for biogas production. As for CMC3, additives can be used if they are compliant with Reach regulation (EC 1907/2006) without exceeding 5% of total digested material biomass. Regulation UE 2019/1009 also specifies digestion conditions for this CMC. No additional thresholds for macroscopic impurities or HAPs are specified for this category.

CMC 5: Digestate other than fresh crop digestate

Compared to CMC 4, this CMC concerns digestate issuing the anaerobic digestion of materials other than plant crops (e.g. sewage sludge digestate, food wastes digestate). The incorporation of biowaste is here allowed, as well as municipal waste, animal by-products or derived products. Additives can be used if they are compliant with Reach regulation (EC 1907/2006) without exceeding 5% of total digested material biomass. Some composted or digested materials can be used to produce this type of digestate.

As for CMC3, thresholds are given:

- Macroscopic impurities (glass, metal or plastic) are limited to 3 g/Kg DM
- The sum of glass, metal and plastics is limited to 5g/Kg DM
- HAPs are limited to 6 mg/Kg DM.

CMC 6: Food industry by-products

This CMC is intended to residual products from the food industry, which can be used as fertilizers. It concerns specific substances such as: (i) food industry factory lime; (ii) molasses from sugarcane or sugar beets; (iii) vinasse; (iv) distilleries' grains from alcoholic beverages; (v) plant extracts having undergone only heat treatment (or heat treatment in addition to processing methods referred to in CMC 2) or (vi) lime from drinking water production.

These materials must be registered in Reach according to EC 1907/2006 including their agricultural use. No additional thresholds are specified for CMC 6.

CMC 7: Micro-organisms

The number of micro-organisms which can be accepted as CMC 7 is limited but this short list could be extended in the future. For the moment, only four microorganisms are listed to improve soil fertility: *Azotobacter* spp, mycorrhizal fungi, *Rhizobium* spp., *Azospirillum* spp.

This CMC concerns whole parts of the microorganism (walls, etc.) in living or dead form, non-harmful residual elements of the media on which they were produced. As they are the result of a fermentation process, the authorised treatments include dehydration or lyophilisation.

No thresholds are specified for CMC 7.

CMC 8: Nutrient polymers

Nutrient polymers are defined as natural or synthetic polymers whose degradation into monomers supplies nutrients to plants. They result in simple degradation products (NH₃, H₂O & CO₂) and can be made up of CMC 1 monomers that act on the release of nutrients (e.g. polyaminoacids, polysaccharides).

Non-soluble polymers are prohibited as well as polymers containing more than 600 ppm formaldehyde. FPR regulation requires also that 60% of the polymer shall be soluble in a phosphate buffer solution (pH 7,5°C) at 100°C. No other thresholds are required, and polymers are not concerned by REACH regulation.

CMC 9: Polymers other than nutrient polymers

CMC 9 includes polymers that improve the physical properties of soil (water retention, structure) or of a fertilizer, by modulating the release of nutrients. This includes coating agents, wetting or retaining agents, binding agents and mulching films. Non-soluble polymers are prohibited.

From 16 July 2026, these polymers shall comply with specific biodegradability criteria, but these criteria are not yet established at the European level. On the other hand, polymers (or their by-products) shall pass a plant growth acute toxicity test, an earthworm acute and reproduction toxicity test and a nitrification inhibition test with soil micro-organisms.

CMC 10: Derived products within the meaning of Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009

This category is intended for products derived from animals (or animals by-products), which are at the end of the production line, which are not intended for human consumption, and which have undergone specific treatments to be used as fertilizers (e.g. bone meal, dried blood, horn powder).

A list of animal by-products accepted as CMC 10 is continuously updated by the European Commission. Currently, only some specific processed manures are included in this CMC.

CMC 11: By-products within the meaning of Directive 2008/98/EC

Compared to CMC 10, the CMC 11 by-products are issued from wastes processed in industry, for instance sewage sludge, steelworks slag, paper mill sludge. Besides, animal by-products, composts, digestates and non-natural, non-biodegradable or non-water-soluble polymers shall be excluded. CMC 11 also concerns some polymers:

- polymers that are the result of a polymerization process that has taken place in nature and that have not been chemically modified according to regulation (EC) No 1907/2006,
- biodegradable polymers,
- polymers with a water-solubility higher than 2 g/L measured at 200 °C; pH 7 and ratio 10 g/1 000 mL for 24h.

To be incorporated into fertilizers, a REACH registration is mandatory FOR CMC 11.

CMC 12: Precipitated phosphate salts and derivatives

These substances lead to precipitated phosphate salts obtained from specific input materials. Allowed materials include (i) specific sewage sludge and wastewaters; (ii) bio-waste as specified in 2008/98/CE regulation, (iii) specific residue from bioethanol and biodiesel production and (iv) specific living or dead organisms. Some incomes like non-biodegradable polymers are also prohibited. Detailed input materials authorised to obtain precipitated phosphate salts are given in the consolidated document of FPR regulation. Precipitated phosphate salts shall be obtained in reactors and under controlled conditions, and temperature under such processes shall be less than 275 °C. Derivatives from precipitated phosphate shall be executed to intentionally modify the chemical composition of the precipitated phosphate salts.

In addition, precipitated phosphate salts shall contain: (i) more than 16% of dry matter of phosphorus (P_2O_5); (ii) less than 3% of dry matter of organic carbon; (iii) no more than 3 g/kg dry matter of macroscopic impurities above 2 mm in any of the following forms: organic matter, glass, stones, metal and plastics and (iv) no more than 5 g/kg dry matter of the sum of the macroscopic impurities.

No pathogens limit is required for CMC 12 but UE fertilizers containing CMC 12 shall not exceed the pathogens limits specified in FPR regulation for *Salmonella* spp, *Escherichia coli* (or *Enterococcaceae*), *Clostridium perfringens* and *Ascaris* sp. viable eggs.

In addition, CMC 12 shall have no more than 6 mg/kg dry matter of PAH16, and the sum of aluminium (Al) and iron (Fe) shall not exceed 10 % of the dry matter.

By the end, CMC 12 materials will require a Reach registration pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006.

CMC 13: Thermal oxidation materials and derivatives

This category covers a wide range of materials produced by high-temperature combustion processes (with O₂), where organic materials are transformed into a complex mixture of inorganic and organic compounds. These materials are often rich in carbon and minerals.

These “ashes or slags” can be obtained from the recovery of various inputs including living or dead organisms, plant waste, incinerable biowaste, residues from microbial processes, sewage sludge, materials from wastewater treatment, wastes. The thermal oxidation shall be done in an incineration or combustion chamber under no-oxygen limiting conditions. These materials shall contain less than 3% dry matter of carbon, 6 mg/kg dry matter of PAH16 and 20 ng /Kg dry matter of WHO toxicity equivalents.

CMC 13 materials will require a Reach registration pursuant to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006. Other requirements concerning chromium (Cr) and thallium (Tl) are required for fertilizers containing CMC 13.

CMC 14: Pyrolysis and gasification materials

The delegated regulation 2021-2088 created this CMC for the inclusion of biochar into fertilizers. It is defined as products obtained by combustion without O₂ (unlike CMC 13), and from the recovery of various inputs like living or dead organisms, plant waste, biofuel production residues, biowaste, pyrolysis/sewage gasification additives. The thermochemical transformation shall be realised under oxygen limiting conditions at least at 180°C for > 2 seconds.

CMC 14 materials require a Reach registration according to Regulation EC N° 1907/2006 and shall contain less than 6 mg/kg dry matter of PAH16 and less than 20 ng /Kg dry matter of WHO toxicity equivalents. Other requirements concerning chlorine (Cl) and thallium (Tl) are required for fertilizers containing CMC 14.

CMC 15: Recovered high purity materials

The materials targeted by CMC 15 must be recovered from waste (input materials other than animal by-products or derived products 1069/2009), gas purification or emission control process from facilities or materials that are not intended for human or animal consumption.

These materials must have a purity of at least 95% dry matter to be considered as recovered high purity materials and a Reach registration is mandatory. Besides, the materials must not exceed the limit values of pathogens, PAH, dioxins and furans, trace metals (Cr, Tl) and chlorine (Cl).

They are for instance ammonium salts, sulphate salts, phosphate salts, elemental sulphur, calcium carbonate and calcium oxide or mixtures thereof (of a purity of at least 95 % dry matter of the material).

2.1.2. Product Function Categories (PFC)

European Regulation 2019/1009 divides fertilizers into seven PFCs, each with its own specific features. This PFC classification allows better understanding of the properties and uses of each product because

each CE fertilizer must mention in its label the PFC category to which it belongs. What's more, each PFC is associated with regulatory requirements in terms of contents and contaminants.

To this day, there are 7 PFCs defined in the 2019/1009 regulation. Some categories are divided into sub-categories (not developed here). Here is a short description of each of them, with examples.

PFC 1: Fertilizers

This category covers products and substances intended to provide plants with the nutrients essential for their growth. It is divided into sub-categories:

- **organic fertilizers (PFC1(A)):** An organic fertilizer is a fertilizer containing organic carbon and nutrients of solely biological origin. It is in solid or liquid form and contains at least nitrogen, phosphorus, or potassium as nutrients. Nutrient contents thresholds are required by the PFR and depend on the form of the fertilizer and on the nutrient element. Maximal contaminant levels are also defined by this regulation and concern trace elements, copper, zinc and pathogens.
- **organo-mineral fertilizers (PFC 1(B)):** Organo-mineral fertilizers are co-formulations of one or more inorganic fertilizer and one or more materials containing carbon end nutrients. As for PFC1(A), it can be liquid or solid form and provides plants with nitrogen, phosphorus or potassium. Organic carbon (Corg) content shall be at least 7,5 % by mass for solid fertilizers and at least 3% by mass for liquid fertilizers. Maximal contaminant levels are also defined by this regulation and concern trace elements, copper, zinc and pathogens.
- **inorganic fertilizers (PFC1 (C)):** Inorganic fertilizers are substances or products containing or releasing nutrients in mineral form. These fertilizers provide plants with macronutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, sulphate, magnesium, or calcium) and/or with micronutrients like copper, zinc, manganese or molybdenum. Minimal nutrients contents are required and depend on the nutrient and on the fertilizer form (liquid or solid). As for the other fertilizers, maximal contaminant levels are also defined by this regulation and concern trace elements and pathogens.

PFC 2: Liming material

These products are intended to correct soil acidity and shall contain calcium or magnesium in oxides, hydroxides, carbonates or silicates forms. The PFR requires specific characteristics to ensure efficacy of liming as neutralising value, grain sizes and reactivity. Also, maximal contaminant levels are defined by this regulation and concern trace elements and pathogens.

PFC 3: Soil improvers

These products should improve or protect the physical, chemical properties, the structure or the soil biological activities. PFR defines maximal contaminant levels for trace elements and pathogens for this PFC. This PFC is divided into two sub-categories: organic improvers or inorganic improvers. Organic improvers shall contain 95% of material in biological origin and shall not contain fossilised or embedded in geological formations other than peat, leonardite or lignite. Inorganic improvers are soil improvers other than the organic soil improvers.

PFC 4: Growing media

These are growing substrates other than soil, used for plants or mushrooms to grow in soilless cultivation. Examples: rock wool, coconut fibre, perlite. FPR defines maximal contaminant levels for trace elements and pathogens for this PFC.

PFC 5: Inhibitors

Inhibitors are intended to slow down specific biological reactions in the soil. This PFC is divided into three subcategories: nitrification inhibitors (PFC 5A); denitrification inhibitors (PFC 5B) and urease inhibitors (PFC 5C). FPR regulation requires efficacy demonstration for each subcategory according to European methods.

PFC 6: Plant biostimulants

A plant biostimulant is a fertilizer used to stimulate plant nutrition processes independently of the product's nutrient content with the sole aim of improving one or more of the following characteristics of the plant or the plant rhizosphere: (a) nutrient use efficiency, (b) tolerance to abiotic stress, (c) quality traits, or (d) availability of confined nutrients in the soil or rhizosphere.

Plant biostimulants stimulate natural processes occurring in the plant or soil rhizosphere and related to a specific claiming. The FPR defines 2 types of plant biostimulants:

- PFC 6 (A) Microbial plant biostimulant:** A microbial plant biostimulant shall consist of a micro-organism or a consortium of micro-organisms referred to in CMC 7. This category must not contain any of the following pathogens: *Salmonella* spp., *Escherichia coli*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Vibrio* spp., *Shigella* spp. and *Staphylococcus aureus*. On the other hand, maximal levels are defined for other pathogens.
- PFC 6 (B) Non-microbial plant biostimulant:** A non-microbial plant biostimulant shall be a plant biostimulant other than a microbial plant biostimulant. Maximal level is defined for *Escherichia coli* or *Enterococcaceae*, and *Salmonella* spp must be absent.

PFC 7: Fertilizing product blend

These are mixtures of two or more EU fertilizers belonging to categories PFC 1 to PFC 6.

2.1.3. PFC labelling and conformity assessment

Producers of European fertilizers must demonstrate that the European fertilizers made available on the market comply with the requirements of the regulation. Also, the competent authorities of the different EU countries need harmonised standards and instructions for the verification of EU fertilizers. The assessment procedures must be proportional to the level of risk involved and the level of security required.

Manufacturers must carry out a conformity assessment procedure before placing EU fertilizing products on the market. The regulation provides four possible procedures:

- Module A: Internal production control
- Module A1: Internal production control plus supervised product testing
- Module B+C: EU type examination followed by conformity assessment by a European notified body. This module can also be chosen by manufacturers instead of module A.
- Module D: Quality assurance of the production process also evaluated by a European notified body.

Table 1: Conformity assessment in UE 2019/1009

Module	Conditions
Module A	PFC1 (excluding fertilizers with a nitrogen content of more than 28 % DM in the form of ammonium nitrate) to PFC 4 and PFC7, if formulated with only CMC1 (excluding inhibitors), CMC4, CMC6, CMC 8 and/or CMC 11
Module A1	PFC1 contains more than 28 % DM nitrogen in ammonium nitrate form
Module B and C	PFC1 to PFC 6 if contained inhibitors, CMC2, CMC4, CMC6, CMC7, CMC8, CMC9, CMC 10 and/or CMC11.
Module D1	All conditions

After successful conformity assessment, manufacturers must draw up an EU declaration of conformity and affix the CE marking to the product in the label.

CE-marked fertilizer must be labelled in accordance with Annex III of the regulation. The labelling requirements are designed to enable consumers to make informed choices about the fertilizers they purchase and use, as well as to ensure that products comply with relevant EU regulations. Key labelling requirements include:

- Physical form of the product
- Production and expiry date
- List of all ingredients, including designations of relevant Component Material Categories (CMCs)
- Application method(s)
- Claimed effects for each plant category (for biostimulants)
- Relevant instructions related to product efficacy, including incompatibilities with plant protection products.
- The label must be in a language easily understood by end-users, as determined by the Member State concerned.

2.1.4. Other Regulations to be considered according to UE 2019/1009

Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH)

REACH is a European regulation that came into force in 2007, and the current consolidated version is dated 10th October 2024¹.

It is intended to identify, evaluate and control chemical substances that are manufactured, imported or placed on the European market; as well as ensuring the safe manufacture and use of chemical substances in European industry. It requires manufacturers and importers of chemical substances in Europe to:

- Register with the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)
- Provide information on the properties and hazards of these substances.
- Assess the risks posed by these substances to human health and the environment.

Depending on the tonnage of the substance, the content of the information to be provided varies; as a minimum, a technical dossier must be drawn up containing the physico-chemical, toxicological and eco-toxicological data for the product. For larger tonnages, a Chemical Safety Report (CSR) is required. This must contain an assessment of the hazards, exposure and risk characterisation.

Once a REACH dossier is submitted to ECHA, the Agency first checks whether the dossier is complete and complies with the regulatory requirements. It then initiates an evaluation process to ensure that the information provided by the registrant is complete, consistent and sufficient to assess the risks associated with the substance in question. ECHA may organise a public consultation to gather the opinion of other interested parties, such as other companies, Member States or non-governmental organisations. If necessary, the Agency may request additional information or carry out a more in-depth assessment. Following this process, ECHA makes a decision on the registration of the substance. It may either accept the registration if the dossier is complete and the risks are deemed acceptable, or request additional information if data are missing or if clarifications are needed, or refuse registration if the risks are deemed unacceptable or the dossier is incomplete. ECHA can also re-evaluate a registration at any time if new information comes to light or if the substance's conditions of use change.

After the substance or mixture has been registered, the information contained in the dossier is incorporated into the ECHA database, which can be consulted by the public via the ECHA website².

¹ Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 (REACH)

² <https://echa.europa.eu/en/reach>

Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures

CLP Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 came into force on 20 January 2009 and gradually replaced the classification and labelling recommended by the Dangerous Substances Directive (67/548/EEC) and the Dangerous Preparations Directive (1999/45/EC) (directives definitively repealed on 1 June 2015).

This regulation establishes the Globally Harmonised System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals, a system set up by the United Nations to identify hazardous chemicals and inform users of these hazards that is also linked to the REACH regulation. The current consolidated version is dated 1st December 2023.

EC Regulations 1069/2009 and 142/2011 on animal by-products

Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009 (and Regulation (EU) No 142/2011 implementing the latter) concerns animal by-products (ABP), i.e. whole bodies or parts of animals (not intended for human consumption) and their derived products. It defines public health and animal health rules aimed at preventing and minimising risks to human and animal health and guaranteeing the safety of the food and feed chain.

Fertilizing products derived from the recycling of animal by-products may be placed on the EU market under certain conditions:

- They are only obtained from category 2 or 3 by-products.
- They have been produced under pressure sterilization (or similar) conditions.
- They come from approved factories.
- They are not used as animal feed (when produced from meat and bone meals)

2.1.5. Organic farming regulation

Under organic production, additional restrictions exist on the use of fertilizers. First, fertilizers need to comply with the general rules detailed above (i.e. regulations on fertilizing products such as former Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003 and present Regulation (EU) 2019/1009; regulations on animal by-products, such as Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009 and Regulation (EU) No 142/2011, in particular Annexes V and XI). In addition, fertilizers need to be listed in Annex II of the “Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/1165” on authorising certain products and substances for use in organic production and establishing their lists, which is regularly updated. The text below refers to the newest update from 15/11/2023. In addition, a preliminary list of new products that are under discussion to be included in Annex II are listed at the end of this section.

Regarding the use of micro-organisms, the regulation states: “Preparations of micro-organisms may be used to improve the overall condition of the soil or to improve the availability of nutrients in the soil or in the crops. They may only be used according to the specifications and restrictions of use of those respective Union and national legislations.” In addition, some more restrictive conditions are specified in Annex II.

Fertilizing products allowed in organic agriculture, which might be relevant to ReLEAF:

In the following, the fertilizer products allowed in organic agriculture are listed, including a description, specific conditions and limits according to Annex II. The products most relevant to ReLEAF are listed first, and other products are listed below.

Chitin (Polysaccharide obtained from the shell of crustaceans): obtained from organic aquaculture or from sustainable fisheries, in accordance with Article 2 of Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013.

Mollusc waste: only from organic aquaculture or from sustainable fisheries, in accordance with Article 2 of Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013.

Recovered struvite and precipitated phosphate salts: products must meet the requirements laid down in Regulation (EU) 2019/1009. Animal manure as source material cannot have factory farming origin.

Humic and fulvic acids: only if obtained by inorganic salts/solutions excluding ammonium salts; or obtained from drinking water purification.

Hydrolysed proteins of plant origin: -

Sawdust and wood chips: wood not chemically treated after felling.

Composted or fermented bio-waste (Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council): Product obtained from separate bio-waste collection at source, which has been submitted to composting or to anaerobic fermentation for biogas production. Only vegetables and animal bio-waste. Only when produced in a closed and monitored collection system, accepted by the Member State. Maximum concentrations in mg/kg of dry matter: cadmium: 0,7; copper: 70; nickel: 25; lead: 45; zinc: 200; mercury: 0,4; chromium (total): 70; chromium (VI): not detectable.

Composted or fermented mixture of vegetable matter: product obtained from mixtures of vegetable matter, which have been submitted to composting or to anaerobic fermentation for biogas production.

Biogas digestate containing animal by-products co-digested with material of plant or animal origin as listed in this Annex: animal by-products (including by-products of wild animals) of category 3 and digestive tract content of category 2 (categories as defined in Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009). Factory farming origin forbidden. The processes must be in accordance with Regulation (EU) No 142/2011. Not to be applied to edible parts of the crop.

Dejecta of worms (vermicompost) and insect frass-substrate mixture: where relevant in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009

Products or by-products of animal origin as below: (Blood meal, Hoof meal, Horn meal, Bone meal or degelatinized bone meal, Fish meal, Meat meal, Feather, hair and skin meal ('chiquette'), Wool, Fur, Hair, Dairy products, Hydrolysed proteins). Maximum concentration in mg/kg of dry matter of chromium (VI): not detectable. Not to be applied to edible parts of the crop.

Products and by-products of plant origin for fertilizers: e.g.: oilseed cake meal, cocoa husks, malt culms.

Algae and algae products: as far as directly obtained by: (i) physical processes including dehydration, freezing and grinding, (ii) extraction with water or aqueous acid and/or alkaline solution, (iii)

fermentation. Only from organic or collected in a sustainable way in accordance with point 2.4 of Part III of Annex II to Regulation (EU) 2018/848.

Composted bark: wood not chemically treated after felling.

Wood ash: from wood not chemically treated after felling.

Egg shells: factory farming origin forbidden.

Biochar – pyrolysis product made from a wide variety of organic materials of plant origin and applied as a soil conditioner: only from plant materials, when treated after harvest only with products included in Annex I. The relevant limits for contaminants set in Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 apply.

Other fertilizing products allowed in organic agriculture:

Farmyard manure: Product comprising a mixture of animal excrements and vegetable matter (animal bedding and feed material). Factory farming origin forbidden.

Dried farmyard manure and dehydrated poultry manure: factory farming origin forbidden.

Composted animal excrements, including poultry manure and composted farmyard manure: factory farming origin forbidden.

Liquid animal excrements: use after controlled fermentation and/or appropriate dilution. Factory farming origin forbidden.

Peat: use limited to horticulture (market gardening, floriculture, arboriculture, nursery)

Mushroom culture wastes: the initial composition of the substrate shall be limited to products of this Annex II (regulation EU 2021/1165)

Guano: -

Soft ground rock phosphate: product obtained by grinding soft mineral phosphates and containing tricalcium phosphate and calcium carbonate as essential ingredients minimum content of nutrients (percentage by weight): 25 % P_2O_5 . Phosphorus expressed as P_2O_5 soluble in mineral acids, at least 55% of the declared content of P_2O_5 being soluble in 2 % formic acid. Particle size: at least 90% by weight able to pass through a sieve with a mesh of 0,063 mm; at least 99% by weight able to pass through a sieve with a mesh of 0,125 mm. Relevant limits for contaminants set in Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 apply.

Aluminium-calcium phosphate: product obtained in amorphous form by heat treatment and grinding, containing aluminium and calcium phosphates as essential ingredients. Minimum content of nutrients (percentage by weight): 30 % P_2O_5 . Phosphorus expressed as P_2O_5 soluble in mineral acids, at least 75 % of the declared content of P_2O_5 being soluble in alkaline ammonium citrate (Joulie). Particle size: at least 90 % by weight able to pass through a sieve with a mesh of 0,160 mm; at least 98 % by weight able to pass through a sieve with a mesh of 0,630 mm. Relevant limits for contaminants set in Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 apply. Use limited to basic soils (pH > 7,5).

Basic slag (Thomas phosphates or Thomas slag): product obtained in iron-smelting by treatment of the phosphorus melts and containing calcium silicophosphates as its essential ingredients. Minimum content of nutrients (percentage by weight): 12% P_2O_5 . Phosphorus expressed as phosphorus pentoxide soluble in mineral acids, at least 75 % of the declared content of phosphorus pentoxide

being soluble in 2% citric acid, or 10% P₂O₅. Phosphorus expressed as phosphorus pentoxide soluble in 2% citric acid. Particle size: at least 75% able to pass through a sieve with a mesh of 0,160 mm; at least 96% able to pass through a sieve with a mesh of 0,630 mm. The relevant limits for contaminants set in Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 apply.

Xylite: only if obtained as a by-product of mining activities (e.g. by-product of brown coal mining).

Crude potassium salt: product obtained from crude potassium salts. Minimum content of nutrients (percentage by weight): 9% K₂O (potassium expressed as water-soluble K₂O), 2% MgO (magnesium in the form of water-soluble salts, expressed as magnesium oxide). The relevant limits for contaminants set in Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 apply.

Potassium sulphate, possibly containing magnesium salt: product obtained from crude potassium salt by a physical extraction process, containing possibly also magnesium salts.

Stillage and stillage extract: ammonium stillage excluded.

Calcium carbonate, for instance: chalk, marl, ground limestone, Breton ameliorant (maërl), phosphate chalk: only of natural origin

Magnesium and calcium carbonate: only of natural origin such as magnesian chalk, ground magnesium, or limestone.

Magnesium sulphate (kieserite): only of natural origin.

Calcium chloride solution: only for foliar treatment of apple trees, to prevent calcium deficit.

Calcium sulphate (gypsum): product of natural origin containing calcium sulphate at various degrees of hydration. Minimum content of nutrients (percentage per weight): 25% CaO, 35% SO₃, calcium and sulphur expressed as total CaO + SO₃. Fineness of grind: at least 80 % to pass through a sieve with a 2 mm mesh width; at least 99% to pass through a sieve with a 10 mm mesh width. The relevant limits for contaminants set in Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 apply.

Industrial lime from sugar production: by-product of sugar production from sugar beet and sugar cane.

Industrial lime from vacuum salt production: by-product of the vacuum salt production from brine found in mountains.

Elemental sulphur: The relevant limits for contaminants set in Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 apply.

Inorganic Micronutrient Fertilizers: The relevant limits for contaminants set in Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 apply.

Sodium chloride: -

Stone meal, clays and clay minerals: -

Leonardite (Raw organic sediment rich in humic acids): only if obtained as a by-product of mining activities.

Organic rich sediment from freshwater bodies formed under exclusion of oxygen (e.g. sapropel): only organic sediments that are by-products of freshwater body management or extracted from former freshwater areas. When applicable, extraction should be done in a way to cause minimal impact on the aquatic system. Only sediments derived from sources free from contaminations of

pesticides, persistent organic pollutants and petrol-like substances. The relevant limits for contaminants set in Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 apply.

Sodium nitrate: only for algae production on land in closed systems

Potassium chloride (muriate of potash): only of natural origin

Selenium salts: only in case of deficiency in the soil used for animal rearing, and/or grazing or the production of feed crops.

Products under discussion to be included in Annex II

In a draft implementing regulation, new products are under review for being added to the Annex II. Currently, a feedback period is open for commenting on these changes³

Carbon dioxide: use for enrichment of water for algae production on land in closed systems; in this case, carbon dioxide shall be of food grade when available, carbon dioxide shall be obtained as a by-product of other processes or from renewable sources pursuant to Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council. May also be used in greenhouse production.

Calcium acetate: only for foliar application on vegetables in greenhouses and on apple trees to prevent deficiency in calcium; obtained from calcium carbonate of natural origin.

Calcium phosphate: only when derived from sewage sludge ash. Only products complying with the requirements of Regulation (EU) 2019/1009.

Plant fiber mats: plant-based fibers, such as hemp fiber, flax fiber, coconut fiber with no addition of any fertilizer, soil conditioner or nutrient nor additives or binders, only mechanically manufactured. Only for sprouted seeds production as an inert medium referred to in Part I, point 1.3(a), of Annex II to Regulation (EU) 2018/848. When available, materials from organic production shall be used.

Calcium and magnesium gluconate: derived from microbial fermentation.

2.2. National regulations and mutual recognition

The UE 2019/1009 regulation is not mandatory, and fertilizer producers can market their products in each European Member State. Mutual recognition is the procedure by which fertilizer producers can legally market their product in another European country if it is already legally marketed in its country of origin.

2.2.1. Mutual recognition

In Europe, the principle of mutual recognition ensures market access for goods that are not, or are only partially, subject to EU harmonization legislation. Regarding fertilizers, products that are already authorized in another Member State of the European Union but are not covered by the FPR regulation

³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/14024-Organic-production-amended-list-of-authorized-products-and-substances_en

are subject to the principle of mutual recognition according to Regulation (EU) 2019/515. However, each Member State has its own national regulation with specific procedures, requirements, and criteria to be met, meaning that the mutual recognition procedure must be approved by the authorities of the Member State of destination. In principle, the competent authority of the Member State of destination shall inform the fertilizer producer of the applicable national technical rules and the authorization procedure. The fertilizer producer may establish a mutual recognition declaration in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2019/515 and contact the competent authority in the Member State of destination before selling the product on that market.

2.2.2. National regulations

Austria

In Austria, (in addition to Regulation (EU) 2019/1009), the regulation of fertilizers is based on:

The Federal Fertilizer Act (*Düngemittelgesetz* 2012), the main framework defining categories, quality, labelling and authorisation procedures.

The Fertilizer Ordinance (*Düngemittelverordnung*), which specifies limit values for hazardous substances and control methods.

The Environmental Protection Act (*Umweltschutzgesetz*), setting out the general principles of environmental protection and specific provisions relating to the use of fertilizers.

Specific regional regulations (which may vary according to the Austrian Länder), particularly for water protection areas or sensitive agricultural areas.

The institutions responsible for Austrian regulations on the authorisation of fertilizer products are the Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Regions and Water Management and the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety.

United Kingdom

Following Brexit (which came into force on 1 January 2021), UK fertilizer regulation has changed:

The UK has established its own regulatory framework, separate from the EU, for the composition, labelling and safety of fertilizers. Products that complied with EU standards before Brexit now require authorization to be marketed in the UK (authorization requirements may vary depending on the type of fertilizer and its components). Sanitary and phytosanitary controls at UK borders have been strengthened, with the gradual implementation of the Border Target Operating Model (BTOM). The UK authorities carry out regular checks and inspections to ensure that fertilizers sold on the UK market comply with the regulations.

UK regulations are drawn up by the Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs (DEFRA).

France

Fertilizer marketing in France is governed by the rural code (Rural Code, Book II, Chapter V: Marketing and use of fertilizing materials, adjuvants for fertilizing materials and growing media L.255-1 to L.255-18). The Order of December 21, 1998, relating to the approval of fertilizing materials and growing

media and the Order of September 2003 relating to the compulsory implementation of standards. (Order of September 5, 2003, relating to the compulsory application of standards). Different standards determine the characteristics of fertilizers that can be marketed without prior authorisation. Fertilizers that do not comply with these French standards may nevertheless be placed on the market following authorisation issued by the competent authorities in accordance with the order of April 1, 2020.

Italy

The Italian regulations, while part of the European Union framework, incorporate specific national features: Italy, like the other Member States, has the option of establishing national rules for fertilizer products that do not fall within the scope of Regulation (EU) 2019/1009, which makes it possible to take into account the specific characteristics of Italian soils and crops. What's more, the Italian government is particularly vigilant about protecting the 'Made in Italy', especially in the agri-food sector.

The authority responsible for authorising fertilizers is the Italian Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forestry.

Netherlands

In the Netherlands, national regulations are heavily influenced by European directives (Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC)) and Regulation (EU) 2019/1009. However, the country has introduced specific measures to meet its environmental and agricultural challenges:

The Netherlands applies strict rules to limit nitrate pollution, particularly in vulnerable zones, resulting in restrictions on the use of nitrogen fertilizers and specific action plans.

The country has also introduced a rigorous policy to control phosphate emissions, particularly in the livestock sector. This includes phosphate production quotas and rules on the spreading of phosphate fertilizers.

The National Fertilizer Act (*Meststoffenwet*) lays down national rules for the production, trade and use of fertilizers.

The Netherlands also has specific rules for the use of organic fertilizers, such as manure and slurry, to minimize environmental risks. It also has a policy of processing these fertilizers to reduce emissions.

Dutch national regulations are therefore characterised by a proactive approach to environmental protection, in particular with specific measures to limit nitrate and phosphate pollution.

Portugal

In Portugal, national regulations complement Regulation (EU) 2019/1009. Additional national legislation covers products not included in the European regulatory framework, adapting requirements to Portuguese soils and crops. Portuguese legislation also incorporates environmental protection measures, in particular in sensitive areas, such as water protection zones). The Portuguese Ministry of Agriculture is responsible for the regulations in force.

Decree-Law No. 30/2022, published on April 11, 2022, sets rules for placing fertilizing materials on the market, ensuring compliance with Regulation (EU) 2019/1009, which governs EU fertilizing products and related market regulations. The Decree-Law sets that non-harmonized fertilizing materials can

only be marketed in Portugal after registration in the National Register of Non-Harmonized Fertilizing Materials, managed by the Directorate-General for Economic Activities (DGAE).

Ordinance No. 185/2022, published on July 21, 2022, defines non-harmonized fertilizing materials, allowed raw materials, and market requirements. A rectification (Declaration No. 22-A/2022, published on September 16, 2022) clarified certain aspects of the ordinance. Only fertilizers listed in Annex I of Ordinance No. 185/2022 and meeting the regulatory requirements can be marketed in Portugal. If a fertilizing product is not listed, manufacturers must apply for its inclusion.

Economic operators must comply with Decree-Law No. 30/2022, including registration and modification submitted via the DGAE portal (registo.fertilizantes@dgae.gov.pt).

The regulatory Authorities in force are the following⁴:

- DGAE (Directorate-General for Economic Activities): Responsible for the registration of non-harmonized fertilizing materials.
- INIAV (National Institute for Agricultural and Veterinary Research): Issues declarations confirming product safety, agronomic efficacy, and soil suitability when requesting the inclusion of a new product in Annex I.
- DGAV (Directorate-General for Food and Veterinary Affairs): Oversees regulations regarding the use of animal by-products in fertilizing materials.
- DGADR (Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development): Responsible for issuing validation documents for organic production certification.

Finally, the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy (PEPAC 2021-2027) promotes the use of bio-based fertilizers to replace synthetic products, to reduce N₂O and NH₃ emissions, enhance soil fertility, carbon sequestration, and water retention. It encourages organic matter transfer from intensive livestock systems to farms and supports environmental investments aligning with national and EU climate goals, including the Farm to Fork (F2F) Strategy.

Poland

In Poland, the Fertilizer Act (*Ustawa o nawozach i nawożeniu*) establishes the main legal framework for the production, marketing and use of fertilizers in Poland. As an EU Member State, Poland must also comply with harmonized European directives and regulations relating to environmental protection, which may have an impact on the use of fertilizers.

The official Polish authority is the Polish Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development.

Spain

In Spain, national regulations on fertilizer products supplement the European framework with specific provisions:

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/14024-Organic-production-amended-list-of-authorized-products-and-substances_en

- The Royal Decree (*Real Decreto 506/2013*) sets out the rules for placing fertilizer products on the market. It defines the types of fertilizer, their composition, labelling requirements and authorization procedures. It considers the specific characteristics of Spanish soils and crops, particularly in Mediterranean regions.
- Regional regulations may exist, as Spain is a country with strong regional autonomy. These regulations may vary from one autonomous community to another.

Environmental protection laws also apply, particularly regarding the use of fertilizers in protected areas and the prevention of water pollution. Spain is also heavily involved in organic farming, so fertilizers used in this sector must comply with specific standards.

Switzerland

In Switzerland, some fertilizers - corresponding to specific PFC or CMC - require authorization. They can only be imported and/or placed on the market if authorization has been granted by the FOAG (Federal Office of Agriculture). The following PFCs are subject to authorization: PFC 3: Soil conditioner, PFC 5: Inhibitor, and PFC 6: Plant biostimulant, as well as the Swiss-specific PFC 101: Recycled fertilizer (except for PFC 101(A) compost and PFC 101(B) digestate), PFC 102: Additive to fertilizer, and PFC 103: other fertilizer. The following CMCs are subject to authorization: CMC 7: Microorganisms, CMC 11: By-products within the meaning of Directive 2008/98/EC, CMC 12: precipitated phosphate salts and their derived products, CMC 13: materials obtained by thermal oxidation and their derived products, CMC 14: materials obtained by pyrolysis or gasification, CMC 15: recovered high-purity materials. In addition, fertilizers consisting of source material that does not correspond to a CMC also need to be authorized⁵.

Some other fertilizer types just need to be registered but not authorised.

2.3. Ingredients in RELEAF project

ReLEAF project aims to produce different ingredients to be used for agriculture. Ingredients can comply with the European regulation 2019/1009 as CMC and/or as PFC (a CMC can be used in any PFC that meets the specific requirements and function of the end product).

Otherwise, ingredients can be used in agriculture (e.g. as pesticide) if they comply with others or as fertilizer at national levels.

2.3.1. Ammonium Sulphate

Ammonium sulphate obtained through membrane-assisted stripping from sewage sludges can comply with CMC 15 of the FPR if its purity is at least 95% in dry matter. For CMC 15, REACH registration is mandatory. Ammonium sulphate can be used as PFC 1 or can be used to formulate PFC 7 fertilizers. Ammonium sulphate is currently not allowed as fertilizer in organic agriculture.

⁵ <https://www.blw.admin.ch/de/duenger>

2.3.2. Struvite

Struvite precipitated from sewage sludges can comply with CMC 12 of the FPR. For CMC 12, REACH registration is mandatory. Struvite can then be used as PFC 1 or can be used to formulate PFC 7 fertilizers. Struvite from sewage sludges is also allowed in organic agriculture.

2.3.3. Humic and fulvic substances (HFS)

HFS recovered from sewage sludges can comply with CMC 1 of FPR. In this case, they should be registered in REACH. HFS can be used as PFC 6 or can be used to formulate PFC 7 fertilizers. HFS can only be used in organic agriculture if they are obtained by inorganic salts/solutions excluding ammonium salts.

2.3.4. Microbial biomass

A microorganism cultivated in a fermenter on a medium containing fish processing wastewater belongs to CMC 7 if it is listed as authorized microorganism strain given in the FPR. In this case this CMC 7 can be incorporated into a fertilizer as plant biostimulant (PFC 6) or can be used to formulate PFC 7 combination of fertilizers. Microbial biomass may be used in organic agriculture, but more restrictive conditions might be specified in Annex II (EU 2021/1165).

2.3.5. Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA)

The PHA recovered from nutrient-exhausted sewage sludge or agri-food residues can comply with CMC 9 (polymers other than nutrient polymers). In this case, its function shall be to control water penetration (coating agent in a PFC 3, which also implies biodegradability criteria), to increase water retention capacity (wetting agent) or as binding agent in a growing medium (PFC 4). Polymers are not covered by REACH regulation. PHA is not directly listed as allowed in organic agriculture, however composted or fermented bio-waste or vegetable matter are listed on Annex II of (EU 2021/1165).

2.3.6. Indole-3-acetic acid (IAA)

IAA extract recovered from food industry residues or mixed food residues could be considered as a CMC 11 (By-products within the meaning of Directive 2008/98/EC). In this case, a REACH registration will be necessary. IAA could be used as a plant biostimulant (PFC 6) or in combination with other fertilizers (PFC 7), however, depending on the characteristics of the final product, it will be necessary to examine other regulations: for now, IAA is not approved in the pesticide database⁶ but it is concerned by maximum residue levels (MRLs) on crop productions (see annex V of the regulation EU 2016/71).

IAA is not directly listed as allowed in organic agriculture, however composted or fermented bio-waste or vegetable matter are listed on Annex II of (EU 2021/1165).

⁶ Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009

2.3.7. Chitosan

In this project, purified chitosan is recovered from the crustacean *Squilla mantis* (mantis shrimp). Due to its origin and production process, chitosan shall be considered as CMC 10 or a non-nutrient polymer (CMC 9) to be used within a formulation of coated fertilizers. In both cases, there is no REACH registration obligation. But chitosan is approved as a basic substance (elicitor) in the pesticide database (Reg. (EU) 2022/456) if its purity exceeds 85%; nevertheless, an EU fertilizer can contain an ingredient registered as an active substance if it does not claim a plant protection function in this product. In organic agriculture, chitin is allowed as fertilizer if obtained from organic aquaculture or sustainable fisheries. Chitosan is not listed as allowed fertilizer, but chitosan hydrochloride is allowed as organic pesticide if derived from organic aquaculture or sustainable fisheries.

2.3.8. Collagen

Fish skin and bone waste are processed to extract collagen, which can then be used as a coating agent for fertilizers (CMC 9). In this case, its function shall be to control water penetration (coating agent in a PFC 3, which also implies biodegradability criteria), to increase water retention capacity (wetting agent) or as binding agent in a growing medium (PFC 4). Polymers are not covered by REACH regulation. In organic agriculture, by-products of animal origin, such as fish meal, are allowed as fertilizer. However, polymers or collagen are not listed as such.

2.3.9. Mulching films and planting pots

Mulching films and planting pots produced in ReLEAF project are not ingredients, but products directly used by farmers. Mulching films can comply with PFC 3 which may contain a polymer in the form of mulch film. The polymer shall comply with the biodegradability criteria defined in the EU regulation 2019/1009.

Planting pots are not strictly fertilizers, but they are used to grow young plants. If the plants with their pots are put in agricultural land, then the pots will provide organic carbon to soils and can be considered as PFC 3. In this case, pots material must comply with PFC 3 characteristics. However, PFC 3 may contain only polymer in the form of a mulch film. In a use in organic agriculture, biodegradable mulch and pots should be listed in the European input list for organic agriculture according to the basic admission criteria⁷.

For mulching films, raw materials may not be GMOs, biodegradability and compliance with limit values for contaminants must be demonstrated. Bleaching of paper is generally not desirable, colouring may be accepted, if there is an agronomic need. Colorants will be evaluated case-by-case. For biodegradable pots, the evaluation is carried out on a case-by-case basis, considering the requirements for mulching sheets. Peat is not allowed as raw material.

⁷ FIBL Europe (2024). Fertilizers, soil conditioners and crop management tools. https://www.inputs.eu/fileadmin/bml-eu/documents/EU-IL_fertilizers_Nov_2024.pdf

3. User requirements

Public perception of BBFs could be influenced by several factors such as awareness or concerns about security and yields, among others. Besides, agri-food sector is highly conservative and not willing to change, thus it is crucial to involve them in early stages of any product development to foster awareness and facilitate the marketability of the BBFs.

3.1. Object

Early engagement with stakeholders is a highlighted element of the ReLEAF project. End-user (i.e. technical farmers) acceptance is a crucial factor for increasing marketability and widespread adoption of BBFs. Since they are the target of the products developed within the project, involving them and collecting their inputs in early stages of the project makes outcomes more likely to be implemented.

3.2. Methodology

In the ReLEAF context, a survey addressed to farmers was developed by ANECOOP to gather information regarding their knowledge about BBFs, their preferences and their willingness to use BBFs.

The survey was available in 7 languages (English, German, Spanish, French, Italian, Polish, and Portuguese)⁹ to reach as many farmers as possible, and was spread among the target audience via the ReLEAF Consortium contacts, the project website (<https://releafproject.eu>) and social media (mainly LinkedIn), fellow projects contacts (e.g. BioSOILUTIONS, FER-PLAY), and relevant platforms (i.e. Biorefine Cluster Europe, European Sustainable Phosphorus Platform).

Moreover, additional data was gathered from the Spanish Living Lab co-creation session organised by BioSOILUTIONS project with the collaboration of ReLEAF, with the presence of farmers in the region of Valencia and Murcia.

3.3. Results from ReLEAF survey to farmers

The survey was answered by 21 people from Spain, France, Switzerland, and the UK, as can be observed in Figure 1. Most of the participants were from Spain and France, where ReLEAF partners (RITTMO in the case of France and ANECOOP in the case of Spain) have a strong relationship with technical farmers. More surveys will be conducted within the project in the framework of T2.2 and T6.4 and reported on D6.5 (M24) and D6.10 (M48).

Figure 1. Geographical distribution of participants

Despite the uneven geographical distribution of participants, the obtained age distribution revealed that all age groups are represented in a similar ratio.

Figure 2. Age distribution of participants

3.3.1. Main crop type

In order to formulate controlled release BBFs that fulfill crop nutrients needs all along the growing cycle, farmers were asked about the main crops they cultivate. The results obtained showed that the main crops are cereals (e.g. wheat, maize, rice), legumes (e.g. alfalfa, beans), and fruits. In general, all the crops will benefit from growth-stage targeted fertilizers, as in the initial phases of the plantation they need nitrogen-rich fertilizing products, while at posterior times, a phosphorus and potassium-rich product is needed.

Figure 3. Crop distribution

According to the answers received, the developed BBFs should have different characteristics depending on the crop.

Cereals

For the production of cereals, a granulated, controlled-release fertilizer with total release time between 5 and 7 months is desired, as they are fertilized one single time with a bottom fertilizer at the beginning of plant cultivation. In addition, as most cereals are rainfed plantation, it is important to provide BBFs that are degradable due to interactions with soil instead of water solubilization.

Legume

Legumes are watered through sprinkler irrigation, thus a liquid fertilizer with variable composition and total release time is desirable, as the fertilizing products composition should be adapted from time to time (normally every 3 – 4 weeks) according to the specific needs of the crop.

Horticulture

Horticulture crops are usually watered through drip irrigation, thus it is desired to use BBFs in liquid form, with low risk of precipitation of its components that could block the emitters.

Oil seed

Oil seed crops can be fertilized using a bottom fertilization strategy or through watering. Thus, both solid and liquid BBFs could be used depending on the specific requirements of the technical farmer.

Citrus, berries and stone fruit

These fruits are watered through drip irrigation thus, as in the case of horticulture, it is desired to use BBFs in liquid form, with low risk of precipitation of its components that could block the emitters.

Grass and hemp

Grass and hemp require a fertilization regime similar to that of legumes, with constant application of fertilizers through irrigation and variable needs.

3.3.2. Knowledge and use of BBFs

More than 80% of participants declared to know what BBFs are, but only 61% of them have used them on their crops, as can be observed in Figure 4.

Figure 4. BBFs knowledge and use

These results highlighted the importance of end-user awareness and acceptance to improve the BBFs' market penetration with widespread adoption regardless of the crop type, region or irrigation methodology, to achieve EU's ultimate target of replacing up to 30% of synthetic chemical fertilizers with BBFs⁸.

Activities linked with co-creation sessions -including technologies (T2.2) and circular business models (T4.3)- and citizen science (T6.4) will be duly designed to fulfil the detected knowledge gap in the technical farmers community.

3.3.3. Types and characteristics of BBFs

Regarding the type of BBFs, bio-based macro and micro-nutrients (e.g. struvite, vivianite, ammonium sulphate) as substitute of synthetic mineral fertilizers are used by only 19% of participants that apply BBFs to their crops while biostimulants (humic and fulvic acids, algae extracts, amino acids, and beneficial microorganisms) are the most widely used BBFs. A minor portion of participants used alternative BBFs such as nettle manure, used for fertilizing grasslands.

Aligned with the findings in the section of BBFs use, the results pointed out the need of a targeted communication strategy to foster the use of bio-based micro and macro-nutrients to achieve the EU goal regarding synthetic mineral fertilizer replacement while the extended use of bio-based biostimulants would allow the reduction of nutrients input in the soil, as established in the Farm to Fork strategy⁹.

⁸ The European Commission. (2016). Press release Circular economy: New Regulation to boost the use of organic and waste-based fertilizers. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_16_827

⁹ https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/farm-fork-strategy_en

Figure 5. Type and format distribution of the BBFs

In addition, liquid fertilizing products seemed to be the most preferable ones, despite data showed no significant differences. This can be caused by the predominance of cereals in the main crop type of questionnaire participants that, as stated in the previous section, prefer the use of long lasting solid controlled-release fertilizers. Thus, it is important to gather more data to obtain solid conclusions that will be updated in upcoming deliverables.

Regarding general characteristics of BBFs, participants highlighted the preference for products with practical benefits like proven effectiveness, affordable price, ease to apply, and compatible with other products (e.g. pesticides) and existing machinery. The origin of the BBF does not play a key role, but the recommendation by a trustworthy third party (e.g. RTO) was mentioned and it could represent a strategy to promote the adoption of novel BBFs.

Figure 6. Results for technical farmers' requirements for BBFs

3.3.4. Reasons to use BBFs

The main reason to use BBFs (or any other input) is to increase the profitability of the plantation, which can be achieved by improving plant growth, increasing production (marketable yield), or reducing the use of chemical fertilizers (and the related cost).

Figure 7. Results of reasons to use BBFs

As can be observed in Figure 7, improving soil quality is also considered of interest as the carbon depletion of the soil, as well as the reduced ion exchange capacity and water retention capacity, affect negatively soil productivity. However, the results pointed out that the environmental impact of the agricultural sector falls behind performance parameters when choosing the nutrient and other inputs for their crops.

3.3.5. Results and Satisfaction

More than 85% of the technical farmers that have used BBFs are satisfied with the obtained results as they perceived improvements in the crops after the use of BBFs, especially in terms of plant growth and marketable yield. Some of them also reported improvements in soil quality, reduced incidence of plant diseases and better crop quality, particularly when dealing with fruits.

Figure 8. Perceived benefits from the use of BBFs

As agri-food sector is highly conservative, it will be crucial to share with technical farmers the insights from ReLEAF WP3 regarding pot tests in an early stage, and afterwards during field trials (in open field days) to showcase the positive impact of applying ReLEAF products. Besides, the data gathered within WP3 will be summarised into practice abstracts or one-pagers in order to provide technical information in an easily understandable way and foster the use of BFFs.

3.3.6. Additional comments

Within the additional comments provided by the questionnaire participants, the most repeated ones are related to the transparency on the composition and fertilizing properties of the BBF, including information regarding: (1) exact composition; (2) transformation process to differentiate processed BBFs from those waste streams with fertilizing properties (e.g. manure); (3) the expected release dynamics for fertilizing elements; and (4) residual nutrient values. This fact highlights the need of performing co-creation sessions and invest in citizen activities as well as practice abstracts to increase the transparency regarding the use of feedstocks, their transformation process, the agronomic properties of obtained BBFs, and the global awareness of technical farmers.

In addition, products aimed to mitigate the negative effects of climate change are also desired by participants. For example, products for breaking the dormancy are specifically required by a participant, as the global temperature increase, reduced the availability of the required bud temperatures between 2 – 7 °C. Within ReLEAF, the effect of biostimulants on abiotic stress (i.e. heat and drought) resilience will be assessed to respond partially to end-user requirements.

Finally, participants ask for a more affordable price and easier logistics facilitating the exchange of BBFs between neighboring countries. Thus, a proper mapping of feedstocks and the availability of a portfolio of technologies suitable to be upscaled is recommended.

3.4. Results from joint co-creation session with BioSOILUTIONS

In this session participated 26 people from different Spanish regions with more representatives from Valencia and Murcia region, as can be observed in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Geographical distribution of participants in the co-creation session

3.4.1. Crop interests

In order to formulate controlled release BBFs that fulfil crops nutrients needs along all the growing cycle, farmers were asked what type of crops they are more interested in. Results showed that farmers

are interested in fruit trees, horticultural crops (e.g. lettuce, tomato), cereals and vineyards, which are aligned with the most demanded agricultural products for exportation.

Figure 10. Most interesting crops for farmers

Obtained results differ slightly from those obtained in the end-user questionnaire reported in the previous section, most possibly explained by the predominance of participants from Murcia and Andalucia, areas very focused in horticulture crops and fruit production.

3.4.2. BBFs preferences

A set of questions regarding BBFs composition, feedstocks source or BBFs delivery state was also included, obtaining a significant consensus between all participants.

For field application, do you prefer solid or liquid products?

Figure 11. Preference on delivery state for fertilizers

Farmers participating in the co-creation session showed a high interest in liquid fertilizers instead of solid ones, mainly due to their ease to be dissolved and applied on field during watering. In this sense, as most of the controlled-release fertilizers are designed to be on solid state due to their polymeric binding agent and coating, it is important to think about liquid form alternatives.

a)

Are you interested in the use of biostimulants?

b)

Would be an issue if biostimulants are produced from animal by-products?

Figure 12. Preference on biostimulants

Besides, more than 90% of participants are interested in the use of biostimulants and most of them show no concern regarding biostimulant's animal origin. However, it is important to find plant-based alternatives (i.e. agri-food residues) to produce biostimulants, especially when dealing with products that aim to be used in organic and regenerative farming systems.

3.5. Conclusions

After processing the data collected with the surveys, a good correlation is observed between ReLEAF and BioSOILUTIONS results, which show there is already a fair adoption of BBFs with a generally positive perception. However, there is still a lack of social awareness even among the target population that needs to be addressed.

Regarding farmers demands, it is clear that the intrinsic characteristics of the BBFs are connected to the irrigation strategies, with a need to produce short-term highly soluble liquid CRF and at the same time provide a proper description of the nutrients release patterns of long-term solid CRF. These requirements are related to the clear interest in practical elements of the BBFs that farmers present, where a need for proven agronomic effects and transparency on products and processes is key. Farmers want safe and tested products that improve their agronomic efficiency and that are suited for their current cultivation methodologies. In that sense, it is interesting to see a general adoption of biostimulants, which are much more prevalent than biobased nutrients and present a very good perception among participants.

ANNEX I: Survey about the use of Bio-based Fertilizers in Agriculture

NOTE: Bio-Based fertilizers are fertilizers produced from waste and/or by-products from different sectors of economic activities.

1. General Data:

- Age:
- Region:
- Main crop type:

2. Knowledge and Use of Bio-Based Fertilizers:

- Do you know what are Bio-Based Fertilizers?
 - Yes
 - No
- Have you used Bio-based Fertilizers on your crops?
 - Yes
 - No
- If yes, how long have you been using them?
 - Less than 1 year
 - 1-3 years
 - More than 3 years

3. Types and Formats of Bio-Based Fertilizers:

- What type of Bio-based Fertilizers do you use? (Select all that apply)
 - Macro and micro nutrients (e.g. struvite, compost...)
 - Algae extracts
 - Humic and fulvic acids
 - Amino acids
 - Beneficial microorganisms
 - Other (please specify): _____
- In which format do you prefer Bio-Based Fertilizers? (Select all that apply)
 - Liquid

- Powder
- Granulated
- Other (please specify): _____

4. Reasons to use Bio-Based Fertilizers:

- What is your main reason for using Bio-Based Fertilizers? (Select all that apply)
 - Improve plant growth
 - Increase resistance to diseases
 - Increase production
 - Improve soil quality
 - Reduce the use of chemical fertilizers
 - Reducing the environmental impact of the activity
 - Other (please specify): _____

5. Results and Satisfaction:

- Have you noticed improvements in your crops since you started using Bio-Based Fertilizers?
 - Yes
 - No
- If yes, what kind of improvements have you seen? (Select all that apply)
 - Increased plant growth
 - Lower incidence of disease
 - Increased production
 - Better soil quality
 - Other (please specify): _____
- Are you satisfied with the results obtained?
 - Very satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Unsatisfied
 - Very dissatisfied

6. Preferences and Expectations:

- What characteristics do you look for in a Bio-based Fertilizer? (Select all that apply)
 - Proven effectiveness
 - Affordable price
 - Ease of application
 - Compatibility with other products
 - Natural origin
 - Other (please specify): _____
- What improvements would you like to see in the Bio-based Fertilizers available on the market?

7. Use of Fertilizers:

- Do you add synthetic fertilizers along with Bio-Based Fertilizers?
 - Yes
 - No
- If yes, what kind of fertilizers do you use? (Select all that apply)
 - Chemical fertilizers
 - Organic fertilizers
 - Other (please specify): _____
- Do you consider the use of fertilizers necessary for your crop?
 - Yes
 - No
- Would you like to have a product that includes synthetic and bio-based ingredients in its formulation?
 - Yes
 - No
- If yes, what type of synthetic fertilizer would you like to see included in the Bio-Based Fertilizers product? (Select all that apply)
 - Nitrogen
 - Phosphorus
 - Potassium

- Micronutrients (e.g., zinc, iron)
- Other (please specify): _____

8. Additional Comments:

- Do you have any additional comments or suggestions about the use of Bio-based Fertilizers in agriculture?

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